

Working poverty in the framework of the anthropology of work

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Abstract

The phenomenon of the working poverty is very important and involves a significant percentage of population in many countries. In this study I sketch, without being exhaustive, the state-of-the-art on working poverty in terms of definition and size. I refer to possible recent correlations of working poverty with the COVID-19 pandemic and with the arise of the digital labour platforms. Then, I recall the difference between labour, work, and action according to Hannah Arendt, together with the concept of anthropology of work of Maria Pia Chirinos. Highlighting the pioneering works of Chirinos, I suggest a picture in which the human being, or the rational animal (Lat.: *animal rationale*; Gr.: *zoon logon echon*, ζῷον λόγος ἔχων), is essentially active also in endeavours devoted to self-preservation and care, such as labour. In such picture, society should take into account the richness of traditions and skills of different types of jobs, also in terms of minimal wage.

Keywords: working poverty; Hannah Arendt; anthropology of work; labour, work, and action.

The phenomenon of the working poverty is widely studied in the literature, with noteworthy works that discuss the shades of the meaning of working poor by taking into account the labour market and local living costs in a certain country, or in certain regions of a certain country [1–3]. Without being exhaustive, I am willing to report some examples of studies on working poors in the literature. Although the definition of working poor is not an easy task and the official measurements are controversial in many countries, we want to give these examples to highlight the importance of the phenomenon.

Ramòn Peña-Casas and Mia Latta have written in 2004 the superb publication *Working poor in the European Union* [1]. In this extensive report the first chapter is focussed on the definition of working poor. After a literature research on the topic, Peña-Casas and Latta could write the minimal conditions that the individual must fulfil to be categorized as working poor:

- “be living in a household considered as poor;
- be working or searching for a job;
- have worked or searched for a job during a period (one month to six months) of the previous year, or have accumulated a corresponding number of working hours.” [1]

There are several estimates of the working poors in different countries and in whole world. Peña-Casas and Latta in Chapter 2 discuss the incidence of working poors in the European Union in 1999, and they report a number of working poors that is around 11 million, corresponding to the 7% of the EU population [1]. Gundogan, Bicerli, and Aydin, at Anadolu University, report that 550 million people in the world are working poors [4] using the working paper written by Steven Kapsos in 2004 [5]. In 2018 Lohmann and Marx [6], mentioning the International Labour Organization (ILO) report of 2014 [7], state that in 2013 839 million people lived with 2 US dollars or less a day. In 2020 Estelle Sommeiller reports own calculations on working poverty based on the employment of EU-SILC Microdata and shows percentages for Spain, Italy, and Portugal around 15% and for Greece around 30% [8].

Jeannette Wicks-Lim (professor at University of Massachusetts Amherst) has written in 2012 the article *The Working Poor A Booming Demographic* [9]. Being an expert of minimum wage, Wicks-Lim focusses on a discussion concerning salary. The employers should align the payment of workers to their increasing production of goods and services. Wicks-Lim reminds the importance of a powerful union movement that should fight against poverty wages, and denounces the absence of such powerful union movement [9].

In 2020 Marianna Filandri and Silvia Pasqua (professors at Università di Torino), together with Emanuela Struffolino (researcher at the Berlin Social Science Center, now professor at Università di Milano), have written the article *Being Working Poor or Feeling Working Poor? The Role of Work Intensity and Job Stability for Subjective Poverty* in which they state “having a job is not a sufficient condition to avoid poverty, either in terms of (monetary) objective or subjective poverty” [10]. Indeed, this aspect leads to an additional degree of freedom in a discussion on working poverty.

The appearance of SARS-CoV-2, and the subsequent pandemic of COVID-19 started in 2020, has strengthened already existing problems [11]. In 2020 Andrea Neri and Francesca Zanichelli, at Banca d’Italia, have written interesting report of the wealth of Italian families [12]. According to Neri and Zanichelli, more than half of the interviewed people (the studied sample includes more than three thousand people) have stated there due to pandemic there has been a contraction of the family income [12].

Finally, the occurrence of platform workers is very recent phenomenon. Many types of works, especially goods delivery, but also text translation and software programming, are coordinated by platforms and algorithms. In 2018 Pesole et al. have written a first technical report on platform work in Europe [13]. In 2020 Urzì Brancati, Pesole, and Fernández-Macías have written a second extensive report on platform workers [14]. In their executive summary they write:

“Digital labour platforms are a new form of coordinating the provision of labour services enabled by the latest technological revolution. Many authors claim that digital labour platforms have the potential to disrupt the world of work, both positively by boosting participation in the labour market through better matching procedures, and negatively by circumventing regulation and lowering the quality of employment.” [14]

The fact that digital labour platforms could circumvent regulation and lower the quality of employment could be a new issue in the labour market. In cases like the one of digital labour platform, we can talk about *technoanomia*, since the fast technological advancement leads to a breakdown of social norms (in this case related to work) {The term *technoanomia* has been already used in 2002 by Francesco Macarone Palmieri in a different context [15]}.

Interestingly, while the phenomenon of working poor has been studied from an economical and sociological point of view, a discussion that highlights the worker dignity, also in terms of reasonable wage tier, supported by philosophical and anthropological pictures of work in the contemporary world is missing. Such pictures would lay the foundations for a more comprehensive understanding of the contribution and the reward of the workers in the society, together with the realization and the happiness of the workers. The publications of Maria Pia Chirinos [16–19], which re-elaborate and criticize the well-known thoughts of Hannah Arendt in *The Human Condition* [20], represent pioneering studies in the anthropology of work.

I briefly recall the difference between labour, work, and action according to Hannah Arendt. Arendt, in *The Human Condition*, distinguishes three different types of human activities: labour, work, and action. Labour is the human activity that is focussed on the biological necessities, on the self-preservation and on the reproduction. Labour can be related to the “social reproduction” mentioned by Nancy Fraser [21]. Work is the human activity devoted to the fabrication of durable objects that will become part of the world. The durability “gives the things of the world their relative independence from men who produced and use them” [20]. Action is the human activity by which humans intersubjectively interact with each other.

I make two initial assumptions in this work: The first assumption is the correlation between working poors and low-skilled workers, since “[w]orkers with low education levels and little or no formal qualifications are more likely to be exposed to flexible employment types and poor income, as well as periodic unemployment spells” [1]. The second assumption can be considered a weaker assumption: I correlate low-skilled work to Arendt’s labour.

Maria Pia Chirinos focusses on human activities depicted by Arendt, highlighting the importance of labour and work. Within this framework, Chirinos, in the anthropology of work, has masterfully developed four theses.

In the first thesis, Chirinos states that it is necessary to recovery the notion of matter in its two realizations: i) as metaphysical principle of substance and power; ii) as alive matter that, together with the soul, allows to talk about functions in the different levels of life.

In the second thesis, Chirinos proposes a model of humanism in which the corporeality, the dependence, and the vulnerability are positive values. Moreover, everyday life has to be a relevant aspect of such model of humanism.

In the third thesis, Chirinos presents the notion of work as an anthropological category, i.e. as a function able to shed light on the specificity of human being: The rational and practical capacity, the power to transform the reality. Thus, work is an instrument to acquire virtues and to generate culture.

In the fourth thesis, Chirinos verifies that this notion of work is present at any level of the human action, even in the types of works that Hannah Arendt, in *The Human Condition*, considers as less representative of human being, i.e. the manual labours that are useful for corporal and daily necessities. [17]

Along with the fourth thesis, Chirinos has stressed how manual labours have been considered less representative of the human being not only by Hannah Arendt. Manual labours have been considered less representative of the human being by the majority of the philosophers. Such picture is highlighted in the historical overviews, of the conceptions of work, sketched by Enzo Rutigliano and by Maria Pia Chirinos.

Work (and labour) in Western culture according to Rutigliano [22]: Enzo Rutigliano gives an overview of labour and work from the Bible and ancient Greeks up to contemporary philosophy. First, Rutigliano stresses a particular meaning of the episode of the sirens and Ulysses in the *Odyssey*: the sirens are a metaphor of the knowledge, and the rowers have wax in their ears to pass unscathed such knowledge. Thus, labour demeans human being. Also in the Bible (Genesis) work is considered a punishment. For Aristotle, the proper endeavour of the human being is the activity of the rational soul. In the Middle Age it is evident the contrast between *vita contemplative* and *vita active*, with the exception of the rule of Saint Benedict "*ora et labora*". With Luther and Calvin work becomes vocation (*Beruf*, which is German means vocation, call, duty). With Locke work is foundation and justification for the property, while for Smith work is primarily a human activity. In Marx, and Hegel, work is again primarily human, but it should be relieved from the rough conditions due to capitalism. Instead, Nietzsche recalls the ancient Greeks: work demeans human being. Last, Rutigliano stresses the bivalent perception of work in the second half of the 20th century: work is not anymore the goal of human being, but it is the material basis for human preservation.

Work (and labour) in Western culture according to Chirinos [18]: Chirinos starts the historical overview from Plato: In the cave people that work are like sleep-walkers, since they do not know the good and the truth. In Aristotle, the human perfection is in the *polis*, as location, and in the *otium* (Gr.: *scholé*, σχολή), as activity. The view of Middle Age by Chirinos is similar to the one by Rutigliano. Interestingly, for Chirinos with Reformation and modern philosophy, especially Descartes, work is considered a proper human activity: a new model of humanism, the *homo faber*, arises [19]. With the technological advancement, work becomes again a mechanical activity. Both Adam Smith and Karl Marx conceive the work as a mere means of production. In the 20th century also the non-manual labours can be monotonous and demeaning (*low-tech* works).

Chirinos states that, many years after the publication of *The Human Condition* by Hannah Arendt, a criticism of Arendt's position, i.e. the distinction between labour and work, cannot be procrastinated. In fact, Chirinos underlines that activity like nutrition, cooking, care of fragile and vulnerable living being unravel a plethora of cultural and historical manifestations, which allow to

talk about arts and traditions in which reason and freedom play a major role. Chirinos states that the fact that labour does not lead to durable products does not diminish the richness of such labour [18]. It is remarkable that Chirinos evens out the *zôon logikon* to the *animal laborans*: labour and work are both human activities. Such activities require practical intelligence, willingness, imagination, sensitivity [18].

In this work, recalling the aforementioned works of Chirinos, I state that the rational animal (Lat.: animal rationale; Gr.: *zoon logon echon*, ζῷον λόγος ἔχων), is essentially active in the labour, in the work, and in the action. There are many straightforward examples. An example that is also mentioned by Chirinos is the endeavour of a cook in preparing dishes. Such activity can be considered as a labour for nutrition and, thus, self-preservation. But in this way we would neglect the ensemble of skills of the cook to make palatable dishes, the cooking traditions and the research and development in gastronomic science [23,24]. Another example is the ability of construction workers in making temporary structures for festival and events, in which activities like the Arendt's action find a suitable environment. Also the skills in organizing an event, in terms of decoration, arrangements of proper items (e.g. stage, seats for the audience, audio system) are remarkable.

Another important aspect is care. The words of Nancy Fraser in *Contradictions of Capital and Care* are absolutely notable. In fact, Fraser states that "social-reproductive contradiction of capitalism lies at the root of the so-called crisis of care" and that without *social reproduction* "there could be no culture, no economy, no political organization" [21] By *social reproduction* Fraser means affective and labour works like birthing and raising children, maintaining households etc.

Thus, the two assumptions that label working poors' jobs, that can be in many cases correlated to Arendt's labour and low-skilled jobs, can be strongly criticized. Society is evidently enriched by the labour related to working poors. This aspect should be recognized and rewarded by the society, also in terms of wage laws that take into account the importance of the labour. On the one hand, it is important to clarify the differences between the outputs of labour, work, and action, according to the distinction of Hannah Arendt. But, on the other hand, the interconnection between such outputs labour, work, and action should take into account, as underlined also by Nancy Fraser, stressing that in many cases the action needs work and labour.

Conclusion

A debate on working poverty has started in the 1970s and 1980s the United States. Nowadays, the concept of working poor has become increasingly applicable in the labour market of developed and developing countries [1]. In this work, I would like to use a different approach in discussing working poverty within the framework of the anthropology of work, developed in the pioneering works of Maria Pia Chirinos. Working poors can be related to low-skilled works, and low-skilled work can be related to Arendt's labour, i.e. the human activity that is focussed on the biological necessities, on the self-preservation and on the reproduction. Such two assumptions can be strongly criticized. In fact, Chirinos sheds light on the importance of labour, which unravels a plethora of human cultures and traditions. I integrate the Chirinos' appreciation of labour stressing that such manual works and care-related jobs are foundational for the human being. The rational animal, *zoon logon echon*, is essentially and entirely active also in the labour. Thus, Arendt's labour should not be labelled as low-skill work and, at the same time, working poors' activities should not be labelled as low-skill jobs. In this picture, the appreciation of the different typologies of jobs, in terms of minimal wage laws and social strategies, should be pursued.

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